

Questionnaire on Health and Management of CATTLE Breeding

Date: ____ / ____ / _____ Operator: _____

The parts in italics are instructions intended for the operator administering the questionnaire and should not be read to the respondent.

Section 1. General company information

110. Herd ID Code _____

Emphasize that the company code will be used only for the purpose of identifying the data, but anonymized and for subsequent analysis in the return of the results.

120. Main production and stabulation type:

For pasture, indicate whether for all groups or only part of the herd and for how long.

¹ Milk, free housing

² Milk, free housing + pasture

¹²¹Pasture: ¹ entire herd ² part of the herd

¹²²Time on pasture: _____ days / months.

³ Milk, tie-stall all year round

⁴ Milk, tie-stall + pasture

¹²¹Pasture: ¹ entire herd ² part of the herd

¹²²Time on pasture: _____ days / months.

⁵ Beef, cow-calf line

¹²³Stabulation: ¹ tie-stall ³ free housing

⁶ Beef, rest stall

¹²³Stabulation: ¹ tie-stall ³ free housing

130. Who are the products usually delivered to?

OBJECTIVE: to collect information on the marketing routes of products and dependence on a single market access point.

¹ Transformer (dairy/slaughterhouse), no.: _____ and company name _____

² Cooperative name _____

³ Intermediary

⁴ Final consumer

⁹⁹ Other _____

140. Are you member of any breeders/producers' association?

¹ Yes ⁰ No.

141. If yes, please specify _____.

142. Are test-day records carried out by the local breeder association?

¹ Yes ⁰ No.

143. Do you give permission to collect and use the data provided by the aforementioned association for the purposes of this research?

¹ Yes ⁰ No.

150. Number of employees of the company: _____.

Consider the time actually dedicated to activities in the company: if other work mark 1/2.

160. Consultants / professionals working in the company

¹ Veterinarians, n.: _____, n. visits/month: _____

² Mangimists, n.: _____, n. visits/month: _____

³ Agronomists, n.: _____, n. visits/month: _____
⁹⁹ Other _____

Section 2. General respondent information

210. Age of the tenant: _____ years.

220. How many years have you been doing this work? _____

221. Have you a family history of breeding management?

OBJECTIVE: to define whether the zootechnical activity was practiced by parents or grandparents and to what extent (primary or ancillary activity).

¹ Yes ⁰ No.

230. Do you have specific training in breeding or farm management?

OBJECTIVE: to collect information on the specific training acquired through structured information channels (vocational school / technical institute courses, degree, courses).

¹ Yes ⁰ No.

231 If yes, please specify _____

240. How much time do you usually spend on farm? _____ hours / %.

250. Is the company your primary source of income?

OBJECTIVE: to clarify the amount of hours dedicated to livestock activity to estimate the economic and labor effort that could be expended during the study.

¹ Yes; ⁰ No.

Section 3. Litter and facilities management

310. Herd population at the time of the visit:

If applicable

Population	N.
¹ COWS	
² CALVES (< 6 MONTHS)	
³ HEIFERS (REPLACEMENT, > 6 MONTHS UP TO 1ST BIRTH)	
⁴ FATTENING BEEFS (MALES and FEMALES > 6 MONTHS)	
⁵ BULLS	
⁶ TOTAL CATTLE	

⁷ Kg milk/cow*day	
------------------------------	--

320. Type of bedding:

- ¹ Litter
- ² Bunks
- ⁹⁹ Other _____

330. Litter material:

- ¹ Straw

- ² Sawdust
- ³ Rice husk
- ⁴ Sand
- ⁹⁹ Other _____

340. Amount of litter per cow per day: _____.

350. Time span between cleanings: _____ days.

360. Presence of infirmary box

- ⁰ No
- ¹ Identifiable if necessary
- ² Permanent, but not for exclusive use
- ³ Permanent and for exclusive use
- ⁹⁹ Other _____

Section 4. Production

MILK

If applicable. More detailed information can be obtained from Breeders' Associations.

410. What is the average duration of lactation? _____ days.

420. What is the average duration of dry period? _____ days.

430. What is the average number of lactations per cow? _____.

440. Presence of milking parlor:

- ¹ Yes
- ⁰ No

441. If no, please specify _____

MEAT

If applicable.

450. What is the average number of animals slaughtered per year? _____.

460. What is the average slaughter weight? _____ Kg.

470. What is the average age at slaughter? _____ months.

Section 5. Feeding

510. Has the composition of the feed been prepared *ad hoc* by species, age, and production category in order to meet the nutritional needs of the different animal populations?

- ¹ Yes
- ⁰ No

511. If yes, it is prepared by:

- ¹ Veterinarian
- ² Mangimist
- ³ Agronomist

- Feed expert
⁹⁹ Other _____

520. How is the feed of animals in production composed? (per day)

¹ Food _____ kg _____

origin: ¹ Produced in the company ² Locally produced ³ Produced in another location.

² Food _____ kg _____

origin: ¹ Produced in the company ² Locally produced ³ Produced in another location.

³ Food _____ kg _____

origin: ¹ Produced in the company ² Locally produced ³ Produced in another location.

⁴ Food _____ kg _____

origin: ¹ Produced in the company ² Locally produced ³ Produced in another location.

⁵ Food _____ kg _____

origin: ¹ Produced in the company ² Locally produced ³ Produced in another location.

⁶ Food _____ kg _____

origin: ¹ Produced in the company ² Locally produced ³ Produced in another location.

530. How many times a day is the feed administered? _____.

Section 6. Reproduction

OBJECTIVE: to collect information on the management of reproduction and highlight health problems in the management of newborns.

610. Type of breeding

¹ Natural copulation

² Artificial fertilization

⁹⁹ Other _____

611. If natural copulation, the males come from:

¹ the same herd and never lent to other herds

² the same herd, sometimes lent to other herds

³ from other herds

620. What is the average age at first fertilization? _____ months

630. What is the average number of calvings per year? _____

640. What is the mean proportion of abortions? _____%

641. Among them, what is the proportion of early miscarriages/resorptions? _____%

642. Among them, what is the proportion of late-term abortions/ stillbirth? _____%

643. Are abortions submitted to pathological examination?

⁰ Never

¹ Seldom

² Often

³ Always

650. How many calves died between 2 and 30 days in the last year? _____ calves

660. Is estrus synchronization protocol applied?

¹ Yes ⁰ No

670. Are pregnant cows moved into a box dedicated to calving?

¹ Yes ⁰ No

671. If yes, how long before? _____ hours / days

672. How long do they stay in the box after giving birth? _____ hours / days

673. How often is the litter of the calving box changed? _____ days

680. At calving, is the quality of colostrum evaluated?

¹ Yes ⁰ No

681. If yes, is there a colostrum bank?

¹ Yes ⁰ No

682. If yes, how is colostrum stored?

¹ Refrigeration

² Refrigeration after pasteurization

³ Freezing

⁴ Freezing after pasteurization

⁹⁹ Other _____

690. How is colostrum administered?

¹ Bucket

² The calf remains under the cow

³ Feeding bottle

⁴ Gavage

⁹⁹ Other _____

Section 7. Animal health

710. Indicate which of the following pathologies are perceived as a problem during last year:

¹Respiratory diseases: ¹ Yes ⁰ No

²Gastrointestinal diseases: ¹ Yes ⁰ No

³Traumatic / orthopaedic disease: ¹ Yes ⁰ No

⁴Reproductive diseases: ¹ Yes ⁰ No

⁵Metabolic diseases / intoxications: ¹ Yes ⁰ No

⁶Clinical mastitis: ¹ Yes ⁰ No

⁹⁹ Other _____

720. Is an antiparasitic treatment plan applied?

¹ Yes ⁰ No

730. Is there a vaccination plan?

¹ Yes ⁰ No

731. Towards which diseases?

¹Bovine Viral Diarrhea (BVD): ¹ Yes ⁰ No

²Infectious Bovine Rhinotracheitis (IBR): ¹ Yes ⁰ No

³Respiratory Syncytial Virus (RSV): ¹ Yes ⁰ No.

⁴Bovine Para-influenza Virus (BPIV3): ¹ Yes ⁰ No

⁵Rotavirus: ¹ Yes ⁰ No

⁶Coronavirus: ¹ Yes ⁰ No

⁷*Escherichia coli* k99 (ETEC): Yes No
⁸*Leptospira* spp.: Yes No
⁹⁹ Other _____

740. Are farm-specific vaccines used?

Yes No

If yes, please specify _____

750. How often are mass milk somatic cells checked? _____ / year

If applicable.

751. By whom?

Breeders' Association

Milking equipment

External laboratory

Dairy

⁹⁹ Other _____

752. What is the mean of somatic cells in the three previous measurements (or geometric mean)?

¹¹Month: _____ ¹² SCC: _____ cells x10³ / ml

²¹Month: _____ ²² SCC: _____ cells x10³ / ml

³¹Month: _____ ³² SCC: _____ cells x10³ / ml

760. How often is the total bacterial load of bulk tank milk checked? _____ / year

If applicable.

761. By whom?

Breeders' Association

Milking equipment

External laboratory

Dairy

⁹⁹ Other _____

762. What was the average of the total bacterial load in the three previous measurements?

¹¹Month _____ ¹²Load: _____ CFU / ml

²¹Month _____ ²²Load: _____ CFU / ml

³¹Month _____ ³²Load: _____ CFU / ml

770. Please, indicate the average annual mortality of adult animals: _____ animals / year.

These include animals found dead, euthanasia, urgency and emergency slaughter.

Section 8. Supplying and biosecurity

810. Please, indicate the average number of new introductions per year or their percentage: _____ animals / %

811. Please, indicate the frequency of new introductions: _____ introductions / year

820. Where are the newly introduced animals usually purchased?

Local herd (< 50km)

- ² Distant herd (> 50km)
- ³ Many different herds
- ⁴ Fair / Market
- ⁹⁹ Other _____

830. Are indemnity certifications requested for purchase?

- ¹ Yes ⁰ No

831. If yes, please specify _____

840. Is there a quarantine when new animals are introduced to the farm?

- ¹ Yes ⁰ No

841. If yes, how long does it usually take? _____ days

842. if yes, how are quarantined animals isolated?

- ¹ In a separate structure from the main one, with dedicated tools
- ² In a separate structure from the main one, with shared tools
- ³ In a box inside the main structure
- ⁹⁹ Other _____

850. Do reared animals encounter wild species?

- ¹ Yes ⁰ No

851. If yes, indicate which species:

- ¹ Red deer / fallow deer
- ² Roe deer
- ³ Mouflon
- ⁴ Wild boar
- ⁵ Small mammals, please specify _____
- ⁶ Wolf
- ⁹⁹ Other _____

860. Do reared animals encounter other farmed species?

- ¹ Yes ⁰ No

861. If yes, the herd has:

- ¹ Separated spaces and dedicated tools
- ² Separated spaces but shared tools
- ³ Partially separated spaces
- ⁴ A single promiscuous space
- ⁹⁹ Other _____

870. Are biosecurity measures applied to the entry of personnel, vehicles and materials into the farm?

- ¹ Yes ⁰ No

871. If yes, please specify:

- | | |
|---|--|
| ¹ Sanification of vehicles: | ¹ <input type="checkbox"/> Yes ⁰ <input type="checkbox"/> No |
| ² Disposable shoe covers: | ¹ <input type="checkbox"/> Yes ⁰ <input type="checkbox"/> No |
| ³ Complete disposable protective clothing: | ¹ <input type="checkbox"/> Yes ⁰ <input type="checkbox"/> No |
| ⁹⁹ Other _____ | |

880. Where does the vehicle stop to collect carcasses?

- ¹ Boundary areas of the farm, where the carcasses are gathered
- ² Internal areas of the farm, where there are no live animals

³ Internal areas of the farm, distant from live animals (> 20 cm)

⁴ Internal areas of the farm, with possible contact with live animals (< 20 cm)

Section 9. Management of fodder resources

910. Please indicate the total cultivated / mowed area: _____ hectares

920. Please indicate the main crop allocation in the current year: _____

Section 10. Wastewater management

1010. Which type of wastewater is produced?

¹ Sewage

² Manure

³ Mixed

1020. What structures are available for wastewater management?

¹ Waterproof platform for manure ¹⁰²¹Storage: _____ days.

¹⁰²²Covering: ¹ Yes ⁰ No

² Sewage tanks ¹⁰²¹Storage: _____ days.

¹⁰²²Covering: ¹ Yes ⁰ No

⁹⁹ Other _____

1030. How is wastewater distributed?

¹ Tanker

² Towed mobile wing

³ Self-propelled mobile wing

⁴ Stationary sprinkler

⁹⁹ Other _____

Section 11. Support & Issues

1110. Does the farm receive any contribution?

¹ Yes ⁰ No

1111. If yes, please specify the proportion: _____%

1120. Do you benefit from support for the management of crops and grazing animals?

¹ Yes ⁰ No

1121. If yes, which:

¹ Technician of professional organization

² Agent or another paid private expert

³ Technician of the consortium for the marketing of products

⁴ Expert not for a fee (e.g. advice from a relative or neighbors)

⁵ Technician for seed companies or other means of production

⁹⁹ Other _____

1130. Is there a business and / or management plan compiled by an expert or professional?

¹ Yes ⁰ No

**INFORMATION PURSUANT TO ARTICLE 13 OF LEGISLATIVE DECREE NO. 196/03 AND REQUEST FOR CONSENT
PURSUANT TO ART. 23 OF D. LEG. 193/2006 (Privacy Code)**

I, the undersigned, _____
owner of the farm _____ company code _____
site in _____
municipality of _____ province _____ ZIP code _____

Declare

to have been fully informed about the activities and analyzes that will be carried out for research purposes in my company and in particular about the methods and purposes of:

- the on-farm inspection for the assessment of animal welfare and biosecurity;
- the collection of health and production data;
- the taking of biological samples;

having received clear and exhaustive answers to my questions during the introductory interview by the staff of the University of Turin who conducted the questionnaire.

Aware that all data and samples collected will be analyzed for research purposes only,

I also declare

to have voluntarily joined the research project "*Valorizzazione dell'allevamento bovino in Garfagnana mediante della valutazione del benessere animale*", having understood its objectives.

Place and date _____

The respondent _____